

1 **T-cadherin is a novel regulator of pericyte function during angiogenesis.**

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12 **Abbreviated title for the running head:** T-cadherin regulates pericyte function.

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21 **Authorship contribution:**

22 Study conception and design: MF; data collection: BD, SP, GMB, SV, OR and MF; analysis
23 and interpretation of results: MF and BD; draft manuscript preparation: MF; critical feedback
24 and discussions: PSD and IM. All authors participated in critical revision of the article.

25

26 **ABSTRACT** (Word count: 243)

27 **Objective:** Pericytes are mural cells that play an important role in regulation of angiogenesis
28 and endothelial function. Cadherins are a superfamily of adhesion molecules mediating Ca^{2+} -
29 dependent homophilic cell-cell interactions that control morphogenesis and tissue remodeling.
30 To date classical N-cadherin is the only cadherin described on pericytes. Here we demonstrate
31 that pericytes also express T-cadherin (H-cadherin, CDH13), an atypical GPI-anchored member
32 of the superfamily that has previously been implicated in regulation of neurite guidance,
33 endothelial angiogenic behavior and smooth muscle cell differentiation and progression of
34 cardiovascular disease. The aim of the study was to investigate T-cadherin function in
35 pericytes. **Methods and Results:** Expression of T-cadherin in pericytes from different tissues
36 was performed by immunofluorescence analysis. Using lentivirus-mediated gain-of-function
37 and loss-of-function in cultured human pericytes we demonstrate that T-cadherin regulates
38 pericyte proliferation, migration, invasion, and interactions with endothelial cells during
39 angiogenesis *in vitro* and *in vivo*. T-cadherin effects are associated with reorganization of the
40 cytoskeleton, modulation of cyclin D1, α SMA, integrin β 3, metalloprotease MMP1 and
41 collagen expression levels, and involve Akt/GSK3 β and ROCK intracellular signaling
42 pathways. We also report the development of a novel multiwell 3D microchannel slide for easy
43 analysis of sprouting angiogenesis from a bioengineered microvessel *in vitro*. **Conclusion:** Our
44 data identify T-cadherin as a novel regulator of pericyte function and support that it is required
45 for pericyte proliferation and invasion during active phase of angiogenesis, while T-cadherin
46 loss shifts pericytes towards the myofibroblast state rendering them unable to control
47 endothelial angiogenic behavior.

48

49 **Keywords:** Cadherins, pericytes, endothelial cells, angiogenesis, vessel-on-a-chip

50

51 **Abbreviations:** ECs, endothelial cells; HUVEC, human endothelial cells from umbilical vein;
52 SMCs, smooth muscle cells; PDGF-B, platelet derived growth factor B; VEGF, vascular
53 endothelial growth factor; TGF- β , transforming growth factor beta; EGF, epidermal growth
54 factor; EGFR, epidermal growth factor receptor; IGF-1, insulin-like growth factor-1; GPI,
55 glycosyl-phosphatidylinositol; PDMS, polydimethylsiloxane; PMA, phorbol 12-myristate 13-
56 acetate; S1P, sphingosine-1-phosphate; MLCK, myosin light chain kinase; MMP, matrix
57 metalloproteinase.

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63 INTRODUCTION

64 Pericytes are mural cells which reside within the vascular basement membrane beneath the
65 endothelium and communicate with endothelial cells (ECs) by forming intercellular adhesive
66 contacts or through paracrine signaling. They play an important role in regulation of
67 angiogenesis, endothelial barrier permeability, vascular tone, and inflammation. Loss of
68 pericyte coverage leads to abnormal endothelial activation and hyperplasia, formation of leaky
69 vasculature and haemorrhage, and have been linked to many pathological conditions such as
70 diabetic retinopathy, pulmonary arterial hypertension, atherosclerosis, tumor angiogenesis and
71 metastasis (1-3). Due to their high phenotypic plasticity and progenitor/stem cell-like
72 properties, pericytes are considered as a potential cell-based therapeutic tool in regenerative
73 medicine (4). EC-pericyte cross-talk is mediated by a complex network of signaling cascades,
74 ligand-receptor pairs, and paracrine loops. Among the best characterized are platelet derived
75 growth factor B (PDGF-B), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), transforming growth
76 factor beta (TGF- β), angiopoietins, Notch, and ephrins (1). In spite of a recent surge of interest
77 in pericyte research, there are still many controversies and "white spots" regarding molecular
78 pathways regulating pericyte function.

79 Cadherins are a superfamily of transmembrane adhesion molecules mediating Ca^{2+} -
80 dependent homophilic cell-cell interactions which regulate tissue morphogenesis, cell sorting,
81 polarity and differentiation (5). Several family members have been identified in the vascular
82 tissue. The best studied are endothelial VE-cadherin which plays an essential role in regulation
83 of vascular permeability and angiogenesis, and N-cadherin which forms adherens junctions
84 between smooth muscle cells (SMCs) and myoendothelial junctions between ECs and SMCs
85 and regulates angiogenesis and SMC migration (6). To date N-cadherin is the only cadherin
86 described on pericytes. It forms heterotypic abluminal adherens junctions between ECs and

87 pericytes and is crucial for vessel maturation during angiogenesis and the maintenance of the
88 vessel integrity (7).

89 In the present study we demonstrate that pericytes also express T-cadherin (H-cadherin,
90 *CDH13*), an atypical member of the superfamily that lacks transmembrane and cytoplasmic
91 domains and is anchored to the membrane *via* a glycosyl-phosphatidylinositol (GPI) moiety
92 (8). T-cadherin-based intercellular contacts are weak due to the structure of the adhesive
93 "pocket" and the absence of a cytoplasmic domain. Therefore, T-cadherin is more likely to
94 function as a signaling receptor rather than as a true adhesion molecule. Indeed, T-cadherin was
95 originally identified as a negative guidance cue for projecting motor neurons (9). It belongs to a
96 structurally heterogeneous group of navigation molecules which are often shared between
97 neurons and ECs and regulate extension and reorganization of vascular and neural circuits. In
98 the cardiovascular system T-cadherin is expressed on ECs and SMCs where its level is
99 increased by oxidative and endoplasmic reticulum stress, and during atherosclerosis, restenosis
100 and tumor angiogenesis (10-14). Ectopic upregulation of T-cadherin promotes EC and SMC
101 proliferation, migration and survival, SMC differentiation and endothelial angiogenic activity
102 (15-28). In ECs T-cadherin also mediates proangiogenic activity of adiponectin (APN), a
103 glucose and lipid metabolism controlling hormone that possesses cardioprotective properties
104 (29). Cumulatively, these data identify T-cadherin as a marker of vascular cell activation and
105 tissue remodeling.

106 The first observation of T-cadherin presence on pericyte-like cells in the aortic intimal
107 subendothelial layer and in adventitial microvessels *vasa vasorum* was made two decades ago
108 (10); however, its functional role in pericytes has never been investigated. The present study
109 aimed to examine T-cadherin expression and function in microvascular pericytes. We also
110 report on our development of a novel multiwell microchannel slide to assay sprouting
111 angiogenesis in mixed endothelial-pericyte cultures in the 3D microenvironment.

112 **METHODS**

113 **Cells.**

114 Primary human ECs from umbilical vein (HUVEC) and primary human placental pericytes
115 were purchased from Promocell (Heidelberg, Germany). Pericytes were characterized by the
116 provider as provider as CD31-/CD34-/CD146+/CD105+ cell population. Placental pericytes
117 were used in most experiments due to easy availability of large cell numbers. Some findings
118 were validated also using human adipose tissue pericytes that were isolated from adipose tissue
119 derived stromal vascular fractions (AT-SVF) (Basel, EK 78/07). The study complies with the
120 Declaration of Helsinki, the local ethics committee approved the research protocols, and
121 informed consent was obtained from all subjects. Pericytes were enriched from the AT-SVF as
122 described before (30) as using magnetic activated cell sorting (MiniMACS® Magnetic
123 Microbeads System, Miltenyi Biotec, Bergish Gladbach, Germany) sequentially using CD34
124 and CD146-specific antibodies (Miltenyi Biotec Cat# 130-113-178, RRID:AB_2726005 and
125 Miltenyi Biotec Cat# 130-120-771, RRID:AB_2752191) according to the manufacturer's
126 instructions. Pericytes were enriched as CD34 negative (CD34-) and CD146 positive (CD146+)
127 cells. As non-adherent cells, possible CD45+ cells were excluded upon further culture steps.

128 HUVEC and pericytes were cultured in Endothelial Cell Growth Medium or Pericyte
129 Growth Medium, respectively (EGM #C-22010 or PGM #C-28040, both from Promocell).
130 EGM-2 medium with Bullet Kit supplement (#C-22011, Promocell) was used in some
131 angiogenesis assays. Cells between passages 2 and 9 were used for experimental studies.
132 HUVEC were cultured on plates precoated with 0.1% gelatin.

133

134 **Vectors.**

135 Lentiviral transduction of HUVEC and pericytes was performed as described before (31, 32).
136 Briefly, for lentivirus production, Lenti-X 293T cells (Clontech/Takara Bio USA, St. Germain-

137 en-Laye, France) were transfected with lentiviral expression vector and 3rd generation
138 packaging plasmids pMDLg/pREE, pRSV-Rec and pMD2.G (Addgene, Watertown,
139 Massachusetts, USA, #12251, #12253 and #12259, respectively) using Lipofectamine2000
140 (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, USA). After 72 hours the supernatant containing lentiviral
141 particles was collected, and lentiviral titer was assessed by ELISA using Quick Titer Lentivirus
142 titer kit (Cell Biolabs, San Diego, USA).

143 mEmerald, mCherry and mCherry-Lifeact-7 coding sequences were subcloned by PCR
144 from pmEmerald-LifeAct-7 (Addgene, #54148) and pmCherry-LifeAct-7 (Addgene, #54491)
145 vectors into a modified pLVX lentiviral expression vector (Clontech/Takara Bio USA) carrying
146 neomycin resistance gene. HUVEC were transduced with mEmerald lentivirus, and pericytes
147 with either mCherry or mCherry-Lifeact lentivirus at a MOI of 1. After 48 hours the medium
148 was replaced, and positive cells were selected for 10 days using 250 ug/ml G418 (Roche
149 Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany).

150 Pericytes labeled with mCherry or mCherry-LifeAct were further transduced to
151 overexpress or silence T-cadherin gene. T-cadherin overexpression (Tcad⁺) was achieved using
152 pLVX-puro lentiviral expression vector (Clontech/Takara Bio) carrying full length human T-
153 cadherin cDNA with empty pLVX-puro vector as control (E). T-cadherin silencing (shTcad)
154 was achieved using pLKO.1-puro lentiviral vector (Sigma-Aldrich, #SHC201, Saint-Louis,
155 USA) carrying T-cadherin short hairpin RNA shTcad1 (GCAGAAAGTGTTCCAT-
156 ATCAACTCGAGTTGATATGGAACACTTTCTGCTTTTT, Mission® shRNA
157 TRCN0000291332, Sigma-Aldrich), shTcad2 (AGGACCAGTCAATTCTAAACT-
158 CTCGAGAGTTTAGAATTGACTGGTCCTTTTTT designed using InvivoGen siRNA
159 wizard), or non-mammalian shRNA as control (shC, Sigma-Aldrich, #SHC002). α -Smooth
160 muscle actin (α SMA) silencing was achieved using pLKO.1-puro lentiviral vector (Sigma-
161 Aldrich, #SHC201, Saint-Louis, USA) carrying α SMA short hairpin RNA (shSMA1

162 GCGTGAGATTGTCCGGGAC-ATCTCGAGATGTCCCGGACAATCTCACGCTTTTT,
163 Mission® shRNA TRCN0000300416, Sigma-Aldrich) or shSMA2
164 (CCTTGAGAAGAGTTACGAGTTCTC-GAGAACTCGTAACTCTTCTCAAGGTTTT
165 (Mission® shRNA TRCN0000300413, Sigma-Aldrich). After transduction at a MOI of 1,
166 positive cells were selected for 7 days with 0.75 µg/ml puromycin (Sigma-Aldrich).

167 Adenoviral vector encoding catalytically inactive GSK3β mutant (KM-GSK3β) was a
168 kind gift of Dr. Kenneth Walsh (Tufts University, Boston, MA, USA). KM-GSK3β and empty
169 vector constructs were amplified in HEK293 cells, purified and titered as described previously
170 (21). Pericytes were incubated with adenovirus at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) 50–100 for
171 12 hours. Under these conditions, the transfection efficiency was 90%.

172

173 **Antibodies.**

174 Supplementary Table 1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7595570>) contains the detailed list of
175 antibodies used in the study with RRID numbers and validation references.

176

177 **Immunocytochemistry.**

178 Cells were plated on round 10-mm glass coverslips precoated with 0.5% gelatin at a density of
179 4×10^3 cells/well. After 48 hours cultures were rinsed with PBS, fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde
180 (PAF), permeabilized in 0.1% Triton X-100/PBS and blocked with 3 % BSA in PBS.

181 Coverslips were incubated with primary antibodies for 2 hours and secondary anti-species
182 antibodies for 1 hour at RT. For negative control samples were incubated with non-immune
183 antibodies from respective species instead of the primary antibody step. All antibodies were
184 diluted in buffer containing 1% BSA, 0.1% Tween-20 and PBS (BSA/PBS-T). The following
185 antibodies were used: goat anti-T-cadherin (R and D Systems Cat# AF3264, 1:200), rabbit anti-
186 tubulin (Sigma-Aldrich Cat# T3526, 1:100), donkey anti-goat Cy3-labelled IgG (Jackson

187 ImmunoResearch Labs Cat# 705-165-147, 1:500), donkey anti-rabbit Alexa Fluor 488 IgG
188 (Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A-21206, 1:500), IgG from goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich Cat#
189 I5256, 1:200), IgG from rabbit serum (Sigma-Aldrich Cat# I5006, 1:100). Filamentous actin
190 was detected using TRITC-conjugated phalloidin (Sigma-Aldrich, 0.5 μ g/ml in FCS). Nuclei
191 were counterstained with Hoechst 33342 (Sigma-Aldrich). Samples were mounted using
192 FluorSave medium (Merck/Calbiochem, Darmstadt, Germany). Images were acquired under an
193 Olympus BX63 fluorescent microscope using 10X or 20X objectives at 512 \times 512 pixels and
194 16-bit and analyzed using CellSens (Olympus, Switzerland) or ImageJ (NIH) software.

195

196 **Immunohistochemistry.**

197 Tissue samples from 6-8 week old female C57Bl/6N mice were kindly provided by Prof.
198 Klaus-Peter Lesch (Würzburg, Germany). Procedures and protocols have been approved by the
199 boards of the University of Würzburg and the Government of Lower Franconia (license 55.2–
200 2531.01-92/13). Human adipose tissue was collected during surgical abdominal fat removal at
201 the Basel University Hospital (Ethical permit ref. 78/07, Ethikkommission beider Basel,
202 Switzerland). Cryosections of brain, heart and adipose tissue (20, 8 and 10 μ m thick,
203 respectively) were cut using a cryostat CM1950 (Leica Biosystems, Muttens, Switzerland).
204 Sections were thawed and dried at RT for 20 min, fixed in 4% PAF for 30 min, permeabilized
205 in 0.3% Triton for 30 min and blocked in PBS supplemented with 2% BSA, 5% goat serum and
206 0.1% Tween-20 for 1 hour. Samples were incubated with primary antibodies overnight at +4°C
207 and secondary antibodies for 2 hours at RT. All antibodies were diluted in BSA/PBS-T buffer.
208 The following antibodies were used: goat anti-T-cadherin (R and D Systems Cat # AF3264,
209 1:100), rabbit anti-NG2 (Millipore Cat# AB5320, 1:100), rat anti-CD31 (BD Biosciences Cat#
210 557355, 1:100), secondary anti-species Alexa Fluor 488-(Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A-
211 21208) , Alexa Fluor 546- (Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A10040) and Alexa Fluor 647-

212 (Molecular Probes Cat# A-21447) labeled antibodies (all 1:500). For negative control samples
213 were incubated only with secondary antibody omitting the primary antibody step. Nuclei were
214 counterstained with Hoechst 33342 (Sigma-Aldrich). Samples were mounted in FluorSave
215 medium, and images were acquired under A1 laser scanning confocal microscope (Nikon
216 Instruments Europe) using 10X or 63X objectives at 512×512 pixels and 16-bit. Z-stacks were
217 acquired at a $3 \mu\text{m}$ step. Brain and heart samples were collected from three animals; adipose
218 tissue was collected from two human donors. For each tissue sample stainings were performed
219 in three independent experiments on nine sections, and representative images were selected.

220

221 **Proliferation assay.**

222 Cells were plated on 96-well plates at a density of 2×10^3 cells/well. After 24 hours (day 1)
223 medium was refreshed, and cells were cultured for 6 days with medium change on every
224 second day. Cell numbers were determined after enzymatic dissociation with 0.25% trypsin/1
225 mM EDTA using the Beckman Coulter Z1 counter and normalized to numbers on day 1.

226

227 **Migration assay, videomicroscopy and analysis of cell morphology .**

228 For analysis of cell morphology pericytes were plated onto 24-well plates at a density of 5×10^4
229 cells/well. After 48 hours cultures were fixed and processed for immunostainings and image
230 acquisition as described above under “Immunohistochemistry”. Images were analyzed using
231 ImageJ software (NIH) with respect to cell area, shape descriptors and plot profiles of F-actin
232 intensity distribution along the line drawn perpendicular to the long axis of the cell body.

233 Cell motility was analyzed using an Olympus IX-81 inverted fluorescent time-lapse microscope
234 in a chamber equipped with the temperature, humidity, and CO_2 concentration controls

235 (Olympus, Switzerland). For wound assay cells were plated onto 24-well plates at a density of
236 2.5×10^5 cells/well. Next day cultures were scratch-wounded, rinsed with PBS and cultured in

237 fresh growth medium. Phase contrast images were taken, and the wound area occupied by
238 migrating cells after 24 hours was measured using CellSens software (Soft Imaging System
239 GmbH, Germany). For live cell imaging mCherry-Life-transduced pericytes were plated onto
240 24-well plates at a density of 5×10^4 cells/well, and time-lapse fluorescence microscopy videos
241 were recorded using 10X objective during 24 hours at 15-min intervals.

242

243 **Spheroid invasion assay in fibrin gel.**

244 Mixed endothelial-pericyte spheroids were prepared using hanging drop method. HUVEC and
245 pericytes (final concentration 5×10^3 cells/ml of each cell type) were suspended in medium
246 consisting of EGM and PGM mixed 1:1 and supplemented with 20% methylcellulose (Sigma-
247 Aldrich #M0512). Resulting suspension was pipetted as 50 μ l drops onto non-adherent 15 cm
248 Petri dishes. The dishes were incubated overnight, spheroids were collected by centrifugation
249 and embedded in fibrin gel as described (18). Gels were overlain with EGM/ PGM mix,
250 cultured for 2 days, fixed with 4% PAF and analyzed under an Olympus IX-81 microscope.

251

252 **Angiogenesis on Matrigel *in vitro*.**

253 50 μ l of growth factor-reduced Matrigel (#356231 Corning®, VWR, Dietikon, Switzerland) per
254 well were added to flat-bottom 96-well plates and let to polymerize for 1 hour at 37°C.
255 HUVEC and pericytes were lifted by trypsin and resuspended in EGM-2 medium (Promocell).
256 100 μ l cell suspension containing 1.5×10^4 HUVEC with or without inclusion of 1.5×10^3
257 pericytes (EC:pericyte ratio = 10:1) were plated on top of Matrigel and incubated for up to 30
258 hours. Endothelial network formation was monitored under an Olympus IX-81 time-lapse
259 microscope equipped with a digital camera, a chamber with temperature, humidity and CO₂
260 controls, and CellSens software (Olympus). Images were quantified using Angiogenesis
261 Analyzer plugin for ImageJ (NIH).

262 **Angiogenesis in a novel multiwell microchannel slide.**

263 4-well glass bottom cell culture slides were purchased from Ibidi (Munich, Germany). 0.8 mm
264 diameter holes were drilled in sides of each well, and 23G hypodermic needles (Terumo, 0.6 x
265 32 mm) were inserted in the holes. Components of SYLGARD[®]184 based elastomeric kit
266 (Sigma-Aldrich) were mixed at a ratio of 10:1 and centrifuged 5 min x 485 g to remove air
267 bubbles. 2 ml of the mix was added per well to fill approximately 2/3 of its volume. Slides were
268 cured at 65°C overnight. Then needles were removed, and a round opening was cut in PDMS in
269 the center of each well using a 6 mm biopsy punch (SmithKline Beecham, UK). Slides were
270 sterilized under UV light for 1 hour and stored until experiments.

271 Sterile 23G needles were inserted in the channels. Rat tail type I collagen (#354236 BD
272 Biosciences) was diluted to 4 mg/ml and pH adjusted to 7.4 according to the product manual.
273 180 µl collagen were pipetted into each well and incubated 1 hour at 37°C. After collagen
274 polymerization the needles were removed. Cultured primary human ECs from umbilical vein
275 (HUVEC) and human placental pericytes were resuspended in endothelial growth medium
276 (EGM) and mixed at a ratio EC:pericytes 7:1. 10 µl of cell suspension (total cell number
277 $8 \times 10^4 / 10 \mu\text{l}$) were injected into the channels using a 10-µl pipette tip. Slides were flipped over
278 3 times during 30 min to ensure uniform cell distribution over the channel surface. After 2
279 hours channels were closed with sterile 22G blunt stubs, and gels were overlain with 500 µl
280 EGM. The following growth factors were included either in collagen prior to polymerization,
281 or in the overlay medium: recombinant human vascular endothelial growth factor-165 (VEGF,
282 50 ng/mL, R&D Systems), phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA, 100 ug/ml), and
283 sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P, 500 nM). At selected time points cultures were fixed, and
284 images were taken using an IX-81 microscope and CellSens software (Olympus). Z-stacks
285 were acquired using A1 laser scanning confocal microscope (Nikon) at a 3 µm step using 10X
286 objective at 512×512 pixels and 16-bit and analyzed using NIS (Nikon), Imaris (Bitplane) and

287 ImageJ (NIH) software. Experiments were repeated four times in duplicates, and two image
288 fields were analyzed for each sample.

289 Various culture media and matrices have been evaluated to find the best combination
290 supporting angiogenesis in the assay. Two types of commercially available endothelial media,
291 EGM and EGM-2 (Promocell), both supported sprouting at a similar rate when used for cell
292 suspension and overlay, but in the case of EGM-2 it was necessary to exclude VEGF from the
293 supplement Bullet Kit to observe good response to VEGF. Collagen I matrix was selected due
294 to its ability to promote formation of a quiescent endothelial monolayer (in contrast, for
295 example, to fibrin that tends to preactivate ECs and therefore is less suitable for analysis of
296 growth factor-induced responses). The choice of collagen concentration was dictated by two
297 factors. On the one hand, matrix stiffness influences angiogenic rates and defines whether ECs
298 migrate as single cells or organize into angiogenic sprouts; on the other hand, pericytes display
299 high matrix remodeling activity and quickly destroy loose collagen gels. We established that
300 the best combination of sprouting and gel stability is achieved at a concentration of 4 mg/ml.

301

302 **Angiogenesis *in vivo*.**

303 Ectopic implantation of Matrigel scaffolds was performed as described (33, 34) with
304 modifications. Animals were treated in accordance with the Swiss Federal guidelines for
305 animal welfare, after approval from the Veterinary Office of the Canton of Basel-Stadt (license
306 #1797). CD-1 Nude female mice at the age of 8 weeks were used. HUVEC and pericytes were
307 mixed at a 3:1 ratio and resuspended in Matrigel (Corning®, #356237) supplemented with 0.5
308 ug/ml FGF-2 (R&D Systems). 70 µl gel drops, each containing 2.7×10^5 cells, were pipetted on
309 glass slides pretreated with Sigmacote® (Sigma-Aldrich) and incubated at 37°C for 1 hour.

310 Polymerized gels were gently detached from glass with a spatula and placed in EGM.

311 Implantation was performed on the same day. Mice were anesthetized with isofluran, an

312 incision was made on the dorsal side, and Matrigel scaffolds were implanted into the
313 subcutaneous pockets formed using blunt forceps. Wounds were closed with surgical clips that
314 were removed after one week. At 2 weeks following surgery mice were euthanized using CO₂,
315 the grafts were harvested and fixed in 4% PAF overnight. Images were acquired using A1 laser
316 scanning confocal microscope (Nikon). Z-stacks were obtained using 10X objective at a 3 μm
317 step at 512 × 512 pixels and 16-bit, processed using NIS (Nikon) or Imaris (Bitplane) software
318 and quantified using Angiogenesis Analyzer plugin for ImageJ (NIH). Experiments were
319 repeated three times; each experiment included six animals, and each mouse was engrafted with
320 four constructs (one subcutaneous pocket above each limb). Implants containing pericyte
321 transductants of different types were randomly distributed across all animals to minimize the
322 influence of inter-animal variation on angiogenesis rates.

323

324 **Immunoblotting.**

325 Immunoblotting analysis of whole cell lysates was performed essentially as described before
326 (24). Briefly, cells were plated onto 6-well dishes at a density of 3x10⁵ cells/well. After 48
327 hours cells were rinsed with PBS and protein were extracted using NP40 lysis buffer (25 mM
328 Tris-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1 mM EDTA, 5% glycerol) supplemented with
329 phosphatase and protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche). After centrifugation the supernatants were
330 collected and protein concentration was determined using BCA protein assay kit
331 (ThermoFisher). Samples (10 μg protein) were subjected to 4-15% SDS/PAGE (Bio-Rad,
332 Hercules, USA) and transferred onto PVDF membranes using Trans-blot turbo blotting system
333 (Bio-Rad). After blocking (5% fat-free powdered milk in TBS with 0.1% Tween-20 for 1
334 hour), membranes were probed with primary antibodies against T-cadherin (R and D Systems
335 Cat# AF3264, 1:1000), T-cadherin (Sigma-Aldrich Cat# SAB1405597, 1:1000), αSMA
336 (Sigma-Aldrich Cat# A2547, 1:2000), phospho-Akt Ser⁴⁷³ (Cell Signaling Technology Cat#

337 9271, 1:1000), phospho-Akt Thr³⁰⁸ (Cell Signaling Technology Cat# 9275, 1:1000), total Akt
338 (Cell Signaling Technology Cat# 9272, 1:1000), phospho-GSK3 β (Cell Signaling Technology
339 Cat# 9336, 1:1000), total GSK3 β (Cell Signaling Technology Cat# 9315, 1:1000), phospho-
340 Erk1/2 (Cell Signaling Technology Cat# 9101, 1:1000), total Erk1/2 (Cell Signaling
341 Technology Cat# 4695, 1:1000), cyclin D1 (Cell Signaling Technology Cat# 2922, 1:1000),
342 integrin β 3 (BD Biosciences Cat# 611141, 1:5000), EGFR (Sigma-Aldrich Cat# HPA018530,
343 1:1:1000). Anti-GAPDH antibody (OriGene Cat# TA802519, 1:10000) was used as loading
344 control. Blots were exposed to peroxidase-coupled secondary antibodies (SouthernBiotech Cat#
345 4050-05 or Cat# 1031-05, all 1:2500). Protein detection was done using Immobilon Western
346 Chemiluminescent HRP Substrate (Merck Millipore). Images were acquired using Gel Doc
347 XR+ Imager system and quantified using Image Lab software (Bio-Rad Laboratories).

348

349 **RT-PCR.**

350 Total RNA from cultured cells was isolated using RNeasy® MiniKit (Qiagen, Hilden,
351 Germany), treated with deoxyribonuclease I and reverse transcribed using GoScript Reverse
352 Transcriptase (Promega, Madison, USA). cDNA was amplified by qPCR using GoTaq qPCR
353 master mix (Promega, Madison, USA) and Vii7 Real-time PCR system (Applied Biosystems,
354 Life Technologies Europe). Gene expression was determined using $\Delta\Delta$ Ct comparative method
355 with GAPDH as housekeeping gene. Primer sequences are available on request.

356

357 **Gene expression profiling by qPCR array.**

358 Total RNA of pericytes transduced with lentiviral particles was extracted and reverse
359 transcribed as described above. Gene expression profiling was performed using RT² profiler
360 Cell Motility PCR Array (Qiagen, #PAHS-128Z) and ABI Vii A7 Real-Time PCR system
361 (Applied Biosystems, Life Technologies Europe). Obtained Ct values were uploaded on to the

362 Qiagen data analysis web portal, and fold change/regulation was calculated by $\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$ method.
363 The p-values were calculated by a Student's t-test of the quadruplicate values for each gene. A
364 Ct cut-off of 35 was set, fold-changes larger than 2 with p-values less than 0.05 were
365 considered statistically significant.

366

367 **Statistical analysis.**

368 Experiments were performed on at least three separate occasions, with triplicates for each
369 experimental point unless otherwise stated. Data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism 8.0
370 software (San Diego, USA). Results are given as mean \pm SD. One-way analysis of variance
371 (ANOVA) followed by Tukey post-hoc testing for multiple comparisons were used. A *P* value
372 <0.05 was considered significant.

373

374 **RESULTS**

375

376 **1. T-cadherin expression in pericytes.**

377 To study whether T-cadherin is present in microvascular pericytes we performed
378 immunohistochemical analysis of human and mouse organs. Positive T-cadherin staining was
379 observed in the mouse heart and brain, and in human adipose tissue (Fig. 1A) where it co-
380 localized with pericyte marker NG2 and, as expected, endothelial marker CD31.
381 Immunofluorescence analysis of cultured primary placental pericytes demonstrated a staining
382 pattern typically observed for T-cadherin in other vascular cell types: the protein was diffusely
383 distributed over the cell body and not enriched at intercellular contacts (Fig. 1B). The levels of
384 endogenous T-cadherin gene (Fig. 1C) and protein (Fig. 1D) in cultured placental (PL-PC) and
385 adipose tissue-derived (AT-PC) pericytes were high (average Ct values 23 and 22, respectively)
386 and comparable to those in the endothelium which served as positive control. Pericytes

387 expressed both major molecular forms of T-cadherin previously described in other cell types:
388 the mature 105 kDa protein and its partially processed 130 kDa precursor which is also present
389 on the cell surface (Fig. 1D).

390

391 **2. T-cadherin regulates pericyte proliferation, migration and invasion.**

392 In order to examine the functional role of T-cadherin in pericytes we established gain-of-
393 function and loss-of-function experimental models using cultured human PL-PC (Fig. 2A).
394 Forced overexpression of T-cadherin was achieved using lentiviral delivery of full-length
395 human T-cadherin cDNA (T-cad⁺). Knockdown of T-cadherin expression was achieved using
396 lentiviral delivery of two different T-cadherin short hairpin RNAs (shTcad1 and shTcad2); cells
397 were transduced with either of the two constructs separately. Both shRNAs displayed similar
398 silencing efficiency and functional effects, so for some experiments described herein only data
399 for shTcad1 are presented. Transductants were used in a panel of *in vitro* assays to evaluate
400 main aspects of cell behavior. T-cadherin overexpression had no statistically significant effect
401 on proliferation (Fig. 2B), but promoted directed migration into the wound area (Fig. 2C).
402 Silencing, on the other hand, strongly inhibited both proliferation and migration (Fig. 2B, C).
403 With respect to cell phenotype and cytoskeleton organization, control empty vector- and shC-
404 transduced cells displayed typical fibroblast-like morphologies (Fig. 2D). T-cadherin
405 overexpression induced cell elongation (Fig. 2C for phase contrast images, 2D for fluorescence
406 images, Fig. 2D for graph showing reduced circularity index) and formation of long thin highly
407 motile processes actively exploring the environment (Supplementary videos 1 and 2 for live
408 cell videomicroscopy of pericytes cotransduced with LifeAct vector and either control empty
409 vector <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7600583> or T-cadherin-overexpressing vector
410 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7600601>, respectively). In contrast, shTcad cells lost the
411 fibroblast-like morphology and became poorly spread (reflected by reduced cell area, Fig. 2D

412 graph). Both T-cad⁺ and shTcad cells exhibited high F-actin positivity in the middle of the cell
413 body as compared to more uniform distribution of actin fibers across the cell in empty vector-
414 and shC transductants (Fig. 2D, images and graph).

415 Cell invasion in a 3D microenvironment was evaluated using the spheroid assay which
416 requires formation of multicellular aggregates followed by embedding of resulting spheroids in
417 3-dimensional gels. This approach is widely used for many cell types, but was problematic in
418 the case of pericytes due to their poor intercellular adhesion properties: multicellular aggregates
419 remained loose and irregular in shape and easily fell apart. To overcome this problem we used
420 mixed endothelial-pericyte spheroids where ECs served as a scaffold for aggregating pericytes.
421 When embedded within the matrix, ECs mostly formed the core of the spheroids while
422 pericytes comprised the outer layer from where they actively invade the gel (Fig. 2E, left
423 panel). T-cadherin silencing or overexpression in pericytes inhibited or promoted pericyte
424 invasion, respectively (Fig. 2E, central panel and graph). Mixed spheroids containing T-cad⁺
425 pericytes developed long branched pseudopods that were completely absent in those containing
426 T-cadherin-silenced pericytes (Fig. 2F). Pseudopod formation in mixed spheroids containing T-
427 cad⁺ pericytes could be inhibited by microtubular depolymerizing agent colchicine, while the
428 non-invasive phenotype of T-cadherin-silenced pericytes reverted to a normal invasive
429 phenotype in the presence of Rho-kinase inhibitor Y27632 (Fig. 2F).

430

431 **3. T-cadherin regulates endothelial-pericyte interactions during endothelial network** 432 **formation on Matrigel.**

433 In order to examine whether T-cadherin regulates pericyte interactions with ECs during
434 angiogenesis we performed Matrigel tube formation assay using mixed cultures of mEmerald-
435 labeled parental HUVEC with mCherry-labeled pericytes transduced with T-cadherin
436 constructs. As demonstrated by time-lapse videomicroscopy, tubular networks in endothelial

437 mono-cultures began to form within 1-2 hours, were fully established 8 hours after plating on
438 Matrigel, and thereafter slowly retracted into unconnected cell clusters (Supplementary video 3,
439 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599620>). Inclusion of control empty-vector transduced
440 pericytes resulted in significantly decreased network formation and faster retraction
441 (Supplementary video 4, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599623>), which is consistent with
442 reported inhibitory effects of pericytes on endothelial angiogenic activity (1). T-cadherin
443 overexpression in pericytes enhanced their inhibitory influence: endothelial networks were less
444 pronounced after 8 hours (Fig. 3A) with almost complete disappearance after 24 hours (Fig.
445 3B). T-cadherin-silenced pericytes, in contrast, failed to attenuate formation of tubular
446 structures, which were still visible at 30 hours when other mixed cultures displayed total
447 network collapse (Fig. 3A, B). T-cadherin effects on tube formation in the mixed cultures were
448 likely related to modulation of pericyte invasion: Tcad⁺ pericytes migrated faster along
449 endothelial tubes, while T-cadherin-silenced pericytes remained as scattered single cells not
450 associated with endothelial structures (Fig. 3C, D).

451

452 **4. T-cadherin regulates endothelial-pericyte interactions during sprouting angiogenesis in** 453 **a microchannel assay of sprouting angiogenesis *in vitro*.**

454 We developed a novel custom-made multiwell slide system to assay sprouting angiogenesis in
455 mixed EC-pericyte cultures (Fig. 4). Each well of the slide contains collagen I gel wherein a
456 microchannel is formed by inserting a microneedle that is removed after gel polymerization,
457 ECs and pericytes are plated into the channel, gels are overlain with medium, and angiogenic
458 sprouting is monitored by microscopy (see Methods and Fig. 4B for detailed step-by-step
459 procedure). Angiogenesis in the novel system was first characterized using parental HUVECs
460 and pericytes (Fig. 5A, B). EC monocultures under control medium culture conditions formed a
461 confluent monolayer on the surface of the channel within 24 hours post-injection. When growth

462 factors were included in the gel or medium overlay, angiogenic sprouting was evident after 24
463 hours or 48 hours, respectively. In both cases sprouts extended in all directions from the
464 microchannel due to fast diffusion of growth factor-containing medium through the hydrogel.
465 VEGF induced sprouting alone and in combination with other agonists, and the best response
466 was observed after treatment with the cocktail containing VEGF, PMA, and SIP (35).
467 Extending sprouts were multicellular, with leading cells exhibiting a typical tip cell
468 morphology with multiple filopodia probing the environment which is consistent with
469 stimulatory effect of SIP on tip cell formation (35). When pericytes were included in the
470 cocultures, they were first associated with the quiescent "vessel" structure and then invaded the
471 gel ahead of ECs even in the absence of growth factors, where they remained either as single
472 cells or in association with endothelial sprouts.

473 We next applied our novel system to further evaluate the role of T-cadherin in
474 endothelial-pericyte interactions (Fig. 5C). Experiments using co-cultures of HUVEC and
475 pericytes transduced with T-cadherin constructs showed that T-cad⁺-pericytes were more
476 invasive as compared to control, while T-cadherin-silenced pericytes were unable to invade,
477 thus mirroring our data obtained using spheroid invasion assay (Fig. 2E). However, ECs
478 demonstrated an inverse angiogenic activity pattern: EC sprout outgrowth was reduced in the
479 presence of Tcad⁺ pericytes and highest in cocultures with shTcad-pericytes, suggesting that
480 inhibition of pericyte invasion by T-cadherin silencing results in a pericyte inability to limit EC
481 angiogenic activity.

482

483 **5. Angiogenesis *in vivo*.**

484 *In vitro* findings were validated using an *in vivo* assay of angiogenesis in subcutaneous
485 Matrigel implants containing a mixture of HUVEC and pericytes transduced with T-cadherin
486 constructs. Confocal microscopy analysis of implants containing HUVEC and control pericytes

487 demonstrated that after 2 weeks ECs formed extensive networks in Matrigel, with pericytes
488 recruited to some endothelial structures (Fig. 6A). Inclusion of control pericytes tended to
489 reduce network formation as compared to endothelial monocultures, although the difference did
490 not achieve statistical significance (Fig. 6B). In the presence of T-cadherin-overexpressing
491 pericytes formation of endothelial networks was further reduced, while cocultures containing
492 pericytes transduced with T-cadherin shRNA displayed angiogenesis rates close to endothelial
493 monocultures (Fig. 6B) supporting, similarly to the *in vitro* data, that T-cadherin silencing in
494 pericytes resulted in pericyte failure to attenuate angiogenesis.

495

496 **6. Signaling pathways regulated by T-cadherin in pericytes.**

497 Our previous studies in ECs, SMCs and tumor cells demonstrated that T-cadherin engagement
498 activates PI3K/Akt/GSK3 β signaling axis. Fig. 7A shows that T-cadherin overexpression did
499 not significantly alter activity of the pathway in pericytes, whereas silencing had a profound
500 inhibitory effect on Akt^{Thr308}, Akt^{Ser473} and GSK3 β phosphorylation. Inactivation of the
501 Akt/GSK3 β axis resulted in prominent downregulation of cyclin D1 levels. Erk1/2
502 phosphorylation, on the contrary, was not influenced either by T-cadherin overexpression or
503 silencing. We observed a reciprocal modulation of T-cadherin and α SMA expression: α SMA
504 levels were markedly upregulated in shTcad-pericytes.

505 Since T-cadherin silencing exhibited more prominent effects on pericyte phenotype and
506 signaling than overexpression, pericytes transduced with T-cadherin shRNA were further
507 analyzed with respect to gene expression by RT² profiler Cell Motility PCR Array that
508 evaluates expression of 84 genes important for migration and invasion. Complete data are
509 presented in Supplementary Table 2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7595609>). Most prominent
510 changes (Fig. 7B) were further validated by PCR (Supplementary Table 3,
511 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7595619>). Three genes displayed statistically significant >2-fold

512 changes for both tested shRNAs: epidermal growth factor receptor (*EGFR*) was upregulated,
513 while integrin β 3 and myosin light chain kinase (MLCK) encoded by *ITGB3* and *MYLK* genes,
514 respectively, were downregulated. Several other genes displayed strong tendency to
515 upregulation (insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) gene *IGF1*, actinin α 3 gene *ACTN3*) or
516 downregulation (genes encoding epidermal growth factor (*EGF*), ezrin *EZR*, and talin *TLN1*),
517 but changes achieved significance only in one of the two tested shRNA constructs.
518 Immunoblotting confirmed downregulation of integrin β 3 protein in T-cadherin silenced cells
519 (Fig. 7A). EGFR protein had the same tendency to upregulation by T-cadherin silencing as
520 EGFR gene which was, however, more prominent and significant for only one of T-cadherin
521 shRNAs (Fig. 7C), while MLCK protein was not consistently modulated (not shown). T-
522 cadherin silencing also induced downregulation of matrix metalloproteinase-1 gene *MMP1* and
523 upregulation of collagen genes *COL15A1* and *COL16A1* (Fig. 7D). For *COL1A1* there was a
524 tendency toward upregulation, albeit not achieving significance, in shTcad1-transduced cells.

525 Apart from T-cadherin, N-cadherin is the only member of the superfamily detected on
526 pericytes. We investigated if there is a relationship between expression of the two proteins and
527 analyzed N-cadherin expression in T-cadherin transductants. There was a small decrease in N-
528 cadherin levels in T-cadherin-silenced cells; however, the difference was minor and mostly
529 observed for only one of the two shRNAs (not shown). Therefore we concluded that at least
530 under our culture conditions T-cadherin does not exert significant effects on N-cadherin
531 expression in pericytes.

532 Since Akt/GSK3 β pathway is strongly affected by T-cadherin silencing, we investigated
533 whether inhibition of GSK3 β may reverse some T-cadherin effects in pericytes. Co-
534 transduction of T-cadherin-silenced cells with adenoviral vector encoding catalytically inactive
535 GSK3 β mutant KM-GSK3 β rescued cyclin D1 levels downregulated by T-cadherin silencing

536 (Fig. 7E) suggesting that Akt/GSK3 β pathway plays the central role in regulation of pericyte
537 proliferation by T-cadherin.

538

539 **7. Regulation of T-cadherin expression in pericytes.**

540 Our previous studies demonstrated that in ECs and SMCs T-cadherin levels are upregulated by
541 serum deprivation and associated cellular stress, while growth factors reverse the effect. We
542 examined whether similar regulatory mechanisms exist in pericytes and subjected parental
543 untransduced pericytes to serum deprivation or growth factors involved in control of
544 angiogenesis (Supplementary Fig. S1A <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599902>). Serum
545 withdrawal slightly increased T-cadherin levels after 48 hours, and treatment with PDGF
546 reversed this effect. The changes were minor, and VEGF and FGF-2 did not modulate T-
547 cadherin expression as compared to respective serum-free control. We conclude that, although
548 displaying the same tendency as in other cell types, growth factors and serum do not exert
549 significant influence on T-cadherin expression in pericytes.

550 Since T-cadherin silencing exert strong effects on α SMA levels, we investigated
551 whether there is a reciprocal relationship between expression of the two proteins. α SMA
552 silencing using shRNAs did not influence T-cadherin protein levels in pericytes
553 (Supplementary Figure S1B <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599902>).

554

555 **DISCUSSION**

556 In the present study we identified T-cadherin as the second member of cadherin superfamily
557 (along with N-cadherin) expressed by microvascular pericytes and demonstrated that it has a
558 prominent effect on pericyte function. T-cadherin knockdown inhibited pericyte proliferation,
559 migration, invasion and interactions with ECs, while overexpression promoted migration,
560 invasion and pericyte-dependent regulation of angiogenesis. These effects were accompanied

561 with reorganization of the cytoskeleton, modulation of cyclin D1, α SMA, integrin β 3,
562 metalloprotease MMP1 and collagen expression and involved Akt/GSK3 β and ROCK
563 intracellular signaling pathways.

564 T-cadherin regulates proliferation and migration in several cell types (rev. in (8)), its
565 effects being dependent on the tissue type and the pathophysiological context (25, 28, 36-38).
566 In vascular ECs and SMCs it promotes cell cycle progression, migration and invasion; in ECs
567 these effects are translated into stimulation of angiogenesis, while in SMCs they represent
568 components of the hyperproliferative repair response to vessel injury that contributes to
569 occlusive vascular disease (18-21, 23-26, 39). The regulation of growth and invasion by T-
570 cadherin in cancer cells is complex: different tumor types display opposite functional outcomes
571 following T-cadherin engagement ranging from inhibition of proliferation and invasion to the
572 acquisition of an aggressive basal stem cell gene signature and the loss of epithelial polarity (8).
573 During formation of neural circuits T-cadherin ligation inhibits motor neuron extension, while
574 *Cdh13* knockout promotes serotonergic innervation of the developing prefrontal cortex (40).

575 The data herein show that T-cadherin effects on pericyte function are similar, albeit not
576 entirely, to those on other vascular cells. We did not observe stimulation of pericyte
577 proliferation by T-cadherin overexpression, while silencing strongly inhibited proliferation. T-
578 cadherin-induced changes in proliferation rates closely matched alterations in Akt and GSK3 β
579 phosphorylation and cyclin D1 levels, and transduction with catalytically inactive GSK3 β
580 mutant could rescue cyclin D1 expression in T-cadherin-silenced cells suggesting that
581 Akt/GSK3 β pathway plays the central role in T-cadherin-dependent regulation of pericyte
582 growth. Interestingly, T-cadherin-silenced pericytes exhibited upregulated expression of *EGFR*.
583 Further studies are needed to establish whether the modulation of growth factor receptor
584 pathways contributes to T-cadherin effects, or simply represents a compensatory attempt to
585 rescue cell growth critically inhibited by T-cadherin knockdown.

586 Cell migration and proliferation are essential components of angiogenesis. Pericytes
587 control sprouting angiogenesis through several mechanisms, all requiring the ability to invade
588 the extracellular matrix. During the initial phase of angiogenesis activated pericytes proliferate,
589 degrade the basement membrane and migrate into the perivascular space determining the
590 location of neovessels and paving the way for endothelial sprouts. Later pericytes are recruited
591 to the endothelial structures, repress endothelial angiogenic activity and promote vessel
592 stabilization (1). Here we show that T-cadherin-overexpressing pericytes migrate more
593 efficiently, while silenced ones completely lose the ability to invade and follow ECs under
594 proangiogenic conditions. Pericyte dysfunction caused by T-cadherin knockdown “releases”
595 endothelial activity and enhances angiogenesis as evidenced through increases in EC network
596 remodeling on Matrigel, and in sprouting angiogenesis in a microchannel model.

597 The best strategy to validate these findings *in vivo* would be the use of *Cdh13* knockout
598 mice; however, currently this approach is not feasible and beyond the scope of the present
599 study due to the absence of the mouse strain with pericyte-specific deletion of *Cdh13* gene.
600 Existing KO mice with global knockout are not suitable since T-cadherin is expressed in other
601 vascular cells such as the endothelium or SMCs, which may affect vessel formation during
602 embryogenesis or experimental angiogenesis. Therefore, we performed *in vivo* analysis of
603 neovascularization in Matrigel xenografts populated with pericytes transduced with T-cadherin
604 constructs. In accordance with the *in vitro* results, we observed increased neovessel formation
605 in xenografts containing T-cadherin-silenced pericytes. Together, these data suggest that T-
606 cadherin expression is needed to maintain the pericyte phenotype that is functionally capable of
607 attenuating endothelial angiogenic behavior.

608 Effects of T-cadherin on pericyte motility were accompanied with reorganization of the
609 cytoskeleton. T-cadherin-overexpressing pericytes acquire an elongated morphology with
610 highly motile "exploring" branched pseudopods, while silenced cells display compact poorly

611 spread shape, intense actin filament staining on 2D surface, and completely lack pseudopods in
612 3D gels. Pseudopods are typical for mesenchymal cells invading soft 3D matrices and are
613 equivalent to lamellipodia, which are observed on stiff 2D surfaces and believed to be an *in*
614 *vitro* artifact. Pseudopod formation is dependent on the interplay between F-actin filaments,
615 microtubule growth and activation of Rho GTPases. Microtubules mediate cytoskeleton
616 compression resistance during cell elongation; their disassembly results in pseudopod loss and
617 suppresses cell motility (41). Microtubules have also been shown to inactivate RhoA/ROCK
618 pathway which regulates pericyte contractility (42), and which hyperactivation may lead to
619 generation of excessive contractile force, inhibition of cell elongation and detachment from
620 ECs, thus increasing vessel permeability (43). Our data show that pseudopod formation in T-
621 cadherin-overexpressing pericytes can be blocked by microtubule-depolymerizing agent
622 colchicine, while the non-invasive silenced phenotype can be rescued by ROCK inhibitor
623 Y27632. Together, these data suggest that T-cadherin knockdown may lead to overactivation of
624 RhoA/ROCK pathway and inhibition of cell spreading, while T-cadherin expression helps to
625 maintain the level of relaxation necessary for polarization and elongation of invading pericytes.
626 T-cadherin silencing may further interfere with migration *via* downregulation of integrin β 3,
627 which promotes motility of many cell types including pericytes and SMCs and is essential for
628 lamellipodia dynamics (44-46).

629 Modulation of T-cadherin expression level also has an effect on pericyte phenotype: the
630 knockout strongly upregulates expression of contractile protein α SMA and collagens and
631 downregulates metalloprotease MMP1. Pericytes are mural cells that display significant
632 phenotypic heterogeneity across the vascular bed. They share some markers and common
633 mesenchymal progenitors with SMCs (47) and have even been proposed to differentiate into
634 mature SMCs (48). Some pericyte subsets, such as transitional pericytes of pre- and
635 postcapillaries, express α SMA (49) and provide structural support and regulate microvessel

636 contractility, while α SMA-negative pericytes retain differentiation plasticity and contribute to
637 tissue regeneration (50). Acquisition of α SMA by pericytes may also be a hallmark of
638 pathological processes in the vessel wall. During wound healing fibroblasts differentiate into
639 myofibroblasts that deposit the extracellular matrix to close the wound. Transition is under
640 control of GSK3 β pathway, and α SMA expression is often used as a surrogate marker of
641 collagen-secreting cells in fibrosis (51). A similar myofibroblast transition process has been
642 reported for pericytes. Acquisition of SMC markers and collagen I secretion by pericytes
643 contributes to scar formation (33), pathological vessel remodeling in pulmonary hypertension
644 (52) and liver fibrosis (53, 54). Our previous studies demonstrated that T-cadherin modulates
645 SMC phenotype (15-17). The ability to switch between the contractile and synthetic states is a
646 fundamental feature of SMC biology. T-cadherin overexpression in SMCs promotes acquisition
647 of a dedifferentiated proliferative and migratory phenotype that contributes to reparative tissue
648 remodeling characterized by downregulation of contractile markers. Silencing, on the contrary,
649 induces the quiescent contractile state that exhibits reduced proliferation, high α SMA
650 expression and is involved in the regulation of vascular tone and the maintenance of vessel
651 structure. “Translation” of this concept to pericytes suggests that high T-cadherin expression is
652 a hallmark of activated migratory pericytes participating in sprouting angiogenesis, while T-
653 cadherin downregulation shifts cells towards the myofibroblast state rendering them unable to
654 invade and control angiogenesis but facilitating tissue repair through secretion of the
655 extracellular matrix. Together, these findings contribute to the view of T-cadherin as a receptor
656 involved in formation of novel multicellular circuits during active tissue remodeling and repair.

657 In conclusion, our data suggest that T-cadherin regulates several pericyte functions in a
658 different manner and through different signaling pathways. Pericyte proliferation is sensitive
659 only to T-cadherin silencing and not to overexpression, with Akt/GSK3 β signaling axis playing
660 the central role in regulation of growth. Migration and invasion, on the other hand, are

661 influenced by both T-cadherin overexpression and silencing and are likely to be controlled by
662 another signaling branch that involves molecules regulating cytoskeleton organization, such as
663 Rho kinase. Further studies are needed to identify molecular mechanisms that mediate T-
664 cadherin effects on the balance between proangiogenic and myofibroblast pericyte phenotypes,
665 as well as on stimuli regulating T-cadherin expression in pericytes. Schematic summary of T-
666 cadherin signaling and functional effects in pericytes is shown in Fig. 7F.

667 During the course of this study we developed a novel multiwell channel slide model of
668 a microvessel. The currently existing *in vitro* assays of angiogenesis have many limitations.
669 Matrigel assay is a generally accepted method to evaluate EC angiogenic activity; however, it
670 does not mimic sprouting angiogenesis and rather reflects the network remodeling step.
671 Furthermore, since Matrigel contains poorly defined mixture of matrix proteins and growth
672 factors secreted by Engelbreth-Holm-Swarm mouse sarcoma, it is not suitable for precise
673 evaluation of angiogenic effects of individual growth factors on already pre-activated cells.
674 Spheroid assay can be used for analysis of sprouting from quiescent ECs; however, as
675 mentioned under Results, mixed EC-pericyte spheroids do not emulate the structure of the
676 vascular wall and display very limited outgrowth of ECs which mostly remain inside of the
677 aggregates. Microfluidic devices are the best for recapitulating multicellular processes in the
678 3D microenvironment. However, they often require complex manufacturing procedures and
679 suffer from irreproducibility issues that has prevented them from being widely used in
680 angiogenesis research. Our approach combines advantages of previously published microfluidic
681 design (55) with those of multiwell slide-based assays. It allows standardized simultaneous
682 analysis of many samples and evaluation of sprouting angiogenesis in live or fixed cultures.
683 Angiogenic outgrowth from the microchannel covered by the quiescent endothelial monolayer
684 with underlying pericytes allows clean and precise analysis of angiogenic responses. The assay
685 is easy to handle, reproducible and can be “tailored” to include any components of interest such

686 as matrix proteins, agonists, inhibitors and stromal cells. This “vessel-on-a-chip” slide may
687 represent a possible off-the-shelf solution for cell biologists with no experience in
688 bioengineering and microfluidics who aim to investigate sprouting angiogenesis and related
689 events in the perivascular niche, or to test novel pro- and anti-angiogenic drugs. Potentially the
690 slide could be adapted for other applications such as analysis of endothelial permeability or
691 studies of endothelial function under flow conditions.

692 In conclusion, this study identifies T-cadherin as a novel regulator of pericyte function.
693 Current data further expand the knowledge on molecular and cellular actions of T-cadherin
694 signaling in the cardiovascular system and identify it as a potential therapeutic molecular target
695 in cardiovascular disease. Ectopic selective upregulation of T-cadherin expression in ECs or
696 pericytes may be a part of therapeutic strategy to orchestrate controlled formation of vascular
697 networks during therapeutic angiogenesis thus promoting tissue repair, or inhibit
698 neovascularization in diseases associated with abnormal vascular tissue remodeling.

699

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707

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709

710

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890

891 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

892 **Figure 1. T-cadherin expression in pericytes.** A: Immunofluorescence analysis of frozen
893 tissues for endothelial marker CD31 (green), pericyte antigen NG2 (red) and T-cadherin
894 (purple). Nuclei are counterstained with Hoechst 33342 (blue). Bar, 10 μ m. Arrows show cells
895 double-positive for T-cadherin and NG2. Stainings were performed on samples obtained from
896 three animals and two human donors; nine sections for each sample were analyzed in three
897 independent experiments. Representative images are shown. B: Immunocytofluorescence
898 staining for T-cadherin (red) in human cultured placental pericytes. N/i IgG, control non-
899 immune antibodies. Bar, 50 μ m. Nuclei are counterstained with Hoechst 33342 (blue). C: PCR
900 analysis of T-cadherin gene expression in human cultured adipose tissue pericytes (AT-PC),
901 placental pericytes (PL-PC) and HUVEC. Expression was calculated as fold difference of $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)}$
902 values normalized to housekeeping gene GAPDH. Average Ct values for T-cadherin
903 gene are indicated to evaluate expression level in different cell types. D: Immunoblotting

904 analysis of T-cadherin protein expression in adipose tissue pericytes (AT-PC), placental
905 pericytes (PL-PC) and HUVEC. Two protein bands correspond to the mature 105 kDa T-
906 cadherin protein and its partially processed 130 kDa precursor. GAPDH was used as loading
907 control. B-D: Experiments were performed in triplicate and repeated three times; for blots and
908 stainings representative images are shown.

909

910 **Figure 2. Analysis of T-cadherin effects on pericyte function *in vitro*.** A: Validation of
911 lentivirus-mediated T-cadherin overexpression (Tcad⁺) or silencing using two different
912 shRNAs (shTcad1 or shTcad2) in placental pericytes by immunoblotting. E, control empty
913 vector; shC, control scramble shRNA. GAPDH was used as loading control. B: T-cadherin
914 effects on pericyte proliferation. Error bars show SD values, statistical significance is indicated
915 for shTcad1 and shTcad2 *vs.* shC. Experiments were performed in triplicate and repeated four
916 times. C: T-cadherin effects on pericyte migration. Error bars show min and max values, and +
917 indicates mean values. Bar, 200 μ m. Note long protrusions developed by Tcad⁺ pericytes
918 migrating into the wound area. D: Morphology of transduced pericytes on 2D surface. Green,
919 immunolabeling for tubulin; red, TRITC-phalloidin staining of actin filaments. Bar, 50 μ m.
920 Graphs show quantitative analysis of cell morphology: cell area, cell shape (circularity index),
921 and F-actin distribution (preferentially in the center *vs.* uniform distribution over the cell body).
922 E: Cell invasion from spheroids in 3D collagen gels. Left panel: an example of a spheroid
923 formed by mEmerald-labeled HUVEC and mCherry-expressing pericytes (overlay of phase
924 contrast and fluorescent images). Central panel and graph: invasion from mixed spheroids
925 formed by HUVEC and transduced pericytes (only red channel for pericytes is shown). Bar,
926 200 μ m. At least 10 spheroids for each experimental sample were analyzed. F: Morphology of
927 transduced pericytes invading in 3D gel from mixed spheroids formed by HUVEC and
928 pericytes transduced with Tcad⁺ or shTcad1 constructs. Note reversal of cell phenotype in

929 samples treated with microtubule-depolymerizing agent colchicine or ROCK inhibitor Y27632.
930 Bar, 50 μm . C-F: representative images are shown. Experiments were performed in triplicate
931 and repeated three times. Graphs show min and max values, and + indicates mean values. *, $p <$
932 0.05; **, $p < 0.01$. ***, $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.001$. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
933 followed by Tukey post-hoc testing for multiple comparisons was used.

934

935 **Figure 3. T-cadherin regulates formation of endothelial networks on Matrigel.** HUVEC
936 were plated on Matrigel as a monoculture (EC only) or as a mixture with pericytes transduced
937 with control empty vector (E), T-cadherin gene (Tcad+), control scramble shRNA (shC) or two
938 T-cadherin shRNAs (shTcad1 or shTcad2) and monitored using time-lapse videomicroscopy.
939 A: Phase contrast images taken 8 hours after plating. Bar, 200 μm . B: Fluorescent images of
940 cocultures (only green channel for mEmerald-expressing HUVEC is shown) and corresponding
941 quantitative data obtained after 24 and 30 hours. Bar, 400 μm . Graphs show min and max
942 values, and + indicates mean values. *, $p < 0.05$. Statistical significance is indicated for Tcad+
943 vs. Empty, and for shTcad1 and shTcad2 vs. shC. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
944 followed by Tukey post-hoc testing for multiple comparisons was used. C: Combined phase
945 contrast and fluorescent images of mEmerald-labeled HUVEC (green) and mCherry-labeled
946 pericytes (red) taken after 8 hours after seeding. Arrows show T-cadherin-overexpressing
947 pericytes recruited to endothelial structures. Bar, 100 μm . D: 3D image reconstructions of
948 confocal microscopy images taken after 8 hours using Imaris software. Combined images of
949 mEmerald-labeled HUVEC (green) and mCherry-labeled pericytes (red), as well as the red
950 channel for mCherry-labeled pericytes only are shown. Note that T-cadherin-silenced pericytes
951 remain scattered and are unable to follow endothelial structures. Bar, 200 μm . A-D:
952 Experiments were performed three times in triplicate, representative images are shown.

953

954 **Figure 4. A novel multiwell microchannel slide for analysis of sprouting angiogenesis.** A:
955 General appearance and schematic representation of the device. B: Step-by-step procedure to
956 construct the 3D vessel in the microchannel slide. Sterile 23G hypodermic needles are inserted
957 into the channel of each well, and the wells are filled with collagen gel. After polymerization
958 the needles are removed, and ECs and pericytes are injected into the channel. Once cells are
959 attached, the channels are closed with blunt stubs, gels are overlain with medium, and
960 angiogenic sprouting is monitored by microscopic observation. PDMS, polydimethylsiloxane.
961

962 **Figure 5. Application of the vessel-on-a-chip slide model for analysis of sprouting**
963 **angiogenesis.** A: “Microvessel” formed by ECs on the inner surface of the microchannel in the
964 absence of growth factors (GFs) after 24h hours and new angiogenic sprouts growing into the
965 gel in response to 50 ng/mL VEGF or a cocktail containing 50 ng/mL VEGF, 100 µg/ml PMA
966 and 500 nM S1P (growth factors included in gels, images taken after 48 hours). Phase contrast
967 images (top) and 3D reconstruction of confocal microscopy Z-stacks (bottom). Bar, 100 µm. B:
968 Phase contrast and high magnification confocal microscopy images (maximum intensity
969 projections) of new angiogenic sprouts formed by mEmerald-expressing HUVEC (green)
970 without or with inclusion of mCherry-expressing control pericytes (red). Arrow, tip cell;
971 asterisk, sprouts covered with pericytes. Bar, 100 µm. C: T-cadherin effects on sprouting
972 angiogenesis. Sprouting from “microvessels” formed by HUVEC (green) and pericytes co-
973 transduced with mCherry and T-cadherin constructs (red). PC-E, control empty vector; PC-
974 Tcad+, T-cadherin gene; PC-shC, control scramble shRNA; PC-shTcad1 and PC-shTcad2, two
975 different T-cadherin shRNAs. Top panels, overview images taken after 48 hours using an
976 Olympus inverted fluorescent microscope IX81. Bar, 200 µm. Bottom panels, confocal
977 microscopy images (only green channel for ECs is shown). Bar, 200 µm. Box: magnified areas
978 of confocal microscopy images (maximum intensity projections) demonstrating the difference

979 in endothelial sprouting in the presence of shC- or shTcad pericytes. Bar, 100 μ m. Graphs
980 present quantitative data for pericyte invasion and endothelial sprouting. *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p <$
981 0.01 ; ***, $p < 0.001$. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey post-hoc
982 testing for multiple comparisons was used. Error bars show min and max values, and +
983 indicates mean values. A-C: Experiments were repeated four times in duplicates, two image
984 fields were analyzed for each point. Representative images are shown.

985

986 **Figure 6. Effects of T-cadherin on angiogenesis *in vivo*.** A: Schematic representation of the
987 assay of angiogenesis in subcutaneous Matrigel implants and typical confocal microscopy
988 images of networks and structures formed by mEmerald-expressing HUVEC (green) and
989 mCherry-expressing pericytes (red). CD-1 Nude female mice at the age of 8 weeks were used.
990 Bar, 100 μ m. B: Angiogenic networks formed by ECs (green) without or with inclusion of
991 pericytes (red) transduced with T-cadherin constructs: PC-E, control empty vector; PC-Tcad+,
992 T-cadherin gene; PC-shC, control scramble shRNA; PC-shTcad, T-cadherin shRNA 1.
993 Maximum intensity projections of confocal microscopy Z-stacks. Bar, 200 μ m. C:
994 Quantification of angiogenesis rates and network characteristics. Mean \pm SD values on dot
995 plots are indicated with red lines. *, $p < 0.05$. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
996 followed by Tukey post-hoc testing for multiple comparisons was used. Experiments were
997 performed three times; each set contained six animals engrafted with four constructs (one
998 subcutaneous pocket above each limb) containing pericyte transductants of different types
999 randomly distributed across the animal group.

1000

1001 **Figure 7. Signaling pathways regulated by T-cadherin in pericytes.** Pericytes were
1002 transduced with lentiviral constructs: PC-E, control empty vector; PC-Tcad+, T-cadherin gene;
1003 PC-shC, control scramble shRNA; PC-shTcad1 and shTcad2, two different T-cadherin

1004 shRNAs. A: Immunoblotting analysis of protein expression in transduced cells. B: Cell Motility
1005 PCR Array analysis of gene expression in pericytes transduced T-cadherin shRNAs. Changes
1006 are expressed as fold regulation vs. shC. C: Validation of changes in EGFR expression in T-
1007 cadherin-silenced pericytes by immunoblotting. Changes are expressed as fold regulation vs.
1008 shC. D: PCR analysis of collagen and MMP gene expression in pericytes transduced with T-
1009 cadherin constructs. E: Effects of GSK3 β inhibition on cyclin D1 levels in transduced
1010 pericytes. Changes are expressed as fold regulation vs. respective empty vector. Adeno-E,
1011 control empty adenoviral vector; adeno-KM- GSK3 β , adenoviral vector encoding catalytically
1012 inactive GSK3 β mutant. B-D: *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$. One-way analysis of
1013 variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey post-hoc testing for multiple comparisons was used. B:
1014 Array analysis was performed in duplicates, error bars indicate SD. C, E, D: Error bars show
1015 min and max values, and + indicates mean values. PCR and immunoblotting experiments were
1016 performed at least three times in triplicate; for blots representative images are shown. F:
1017 Schematic diagram of T-cadherin signaling effects in pericytes. Akt/GSK3 β axis mediates T-
1018 cadherin effects on proliferation, while migration and invasion are controlled by pathways
1019 regulating cytoskeleton organization, such as Rho kinase. Both proliferation and migration
1020 contribute to angiogenesis. T-cadherin also regulates expression of myofibroblast markers thus
1021 modulating the balance between proangiogenic and fibrotic pericyte phenotypes.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

A

B

Figure 5

Figure 6

A

B

C

E

D

F

Adhesion molecule T-cadherin regulates pericyte function.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Atypical GPI-anchored adhesion molecule T-cadherin is expressed on pericytes. Its function is unknown.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Lentiviral transduction of pericytes

Studies *in vitro* and *in vivo*

Novel «vessel-on-a-chip» multiwell slide

CONCLUSION

T-cadherin is required for pericyte proliferation, invasion and interactions with endothelial cells during angiogenesis.